

EOSC - Connecting Research Services

Interview with Luciano Gaido, INFN (Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare) / EOSC-Pillar

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Julia

Hello and welcome to today's episode of Stories of Data - The Open Science Talk. I'm Julia Geistberger.

Marie

And I'm Marie Czuray.

Julia

And this time, we have the honor to welcome another guest to our show - Luciano Gaido, Director of Technology at the [Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare, the INFN, in Torino, Italy](#). Ciao, Luciano and welcome!

Luciano

Ciao!

Marie

So, let's get started right away, and talk about your connection to the European Open Science Cloud. How did your story with EOSC-Pillar begin?

Luciano

I have been involved in EOSC-Pillar since the beginning, when the proposal was prepared. The goal was to define some actions to support the main actors in the countries participating to the project in their journey towards the EOSC. As you probably know, EOSC was quite a vague concept, so it was really important to work together with the researchers and with the user communities to help them understand how they can be part of EOSC.

Julia

And now that the project is ongoing, what exactly do you do in EOSC-Pillar – Please describe your work?

Luciano

In EOSC-Pillar, I am coordinating two tasks. The first one (T4.3) concerns the support for the consolidation of National Initiatives which are one of the main actors for the connecting countries to EOSC. Although there may be different types of national initiatives in the countries, in terms of scope, objectives and maturity, we aim to provide support specifically for the consolidation of the so-called

Mandated Initiatives, which play a specific role in the EOSC Association, which is the organisation governing EOSC, because they represent the interests and needs of the different countries.

At a more technical level, I am coordinating task 7.1, which provides technical support for the connection of service providers with EOSC. This means either supporting the onboarding of their services into the EOSC catalogue or any other 'EOSC-recognized' catalogue or to support the integration of services available at the national level with the so-called EOSC Core services. These EOSC Core services are meant to allow for the federation of services in the EOSC ecosystem and will provide interoperability between the services.

Julia

Who benefits from your work?

Luciano

Well, a lot of different actors ranging from individual service providers to organised service providers belonging to thematic, national or international infrastructures and national initiatives.

Julia

Ok, so the first beneficiaries are the providers of research supporting services, but then in the next step I suppose that also researchers benefit from the integration of these services into EOSC, right?

Luciano

Correct. The activities we are doing to support the service providers have an indirect impact on the researchers because as soon as a new service provider advertises their services through the EOSC portal or catalogue, these resources are directly usable by the researchers. So this indirect support for researchers is already there.

Julia

Yeah, that's what EOSC is all about, to make research easier. How do you secure the sustainability of your work?

Luciano

Well, the work done within EOSC Future is very important, and these activities are performed in close collaboration with other actors, specifically with the other regional projects covering other countries in Europe, and also with the flagship project concerning the EOSC: Until April 2021, the flagship project was EOSC Hub, but after its end, a new flagship project called EOSC Future took over the responsibilities and main activities of EOSC Hub. The close collaboration ensures the continuity of the activities, even if there is no follow-up project foreseen for EOSC-Pillar and the other regional projects.

Another important connection is the participation of several EOSC-Pillar members, including myself, to the advisory groups and task forces set up by the EOSC Association. There are many of these task forces

devoted to different tasks in different activities, but one which is very important in my opinion is the task force concerning the rules of participation.

Julia

Well maybe that would be content for another podcast episode, the rules of participation in EOSC. Ok, but for now, I think EOSC Future is a project that we should keep our eyes on, definitely. And apart from that, is there any cooperation with other EOSC services already?

Luciano

Sure. The support for the integration with EOSC Core services as already part of this, but within EOSC-Pillar the services developed in the different work packages are beneficial for other services in other work packages and this is done through regular meetings and workshops organised by the EOSC-Pillar technical board. So the exchange of information and cooperation between actors in the same project and also beyond the boundaries of EOSC-Pillar is foreseen to avoid creating silos.

Unfortunately, we know the silos are already there, because it is what happens within the user communities: They are usually working to develop the services they need for their own work, but with this “contamination” between different communities and activities, we try to avoid consolidating these silos. Also, we make the services developed by certain communities accessible and usable by different communities, in order to achieve an environment, where there is diversity, collaboration and cooperation.

Julia

So, breaking down the boarders between the user communities, that’s what we should all aim for. And speaking of the work you achieved so far, what are you most proud of?

Luciano

Well, the EOSC landscape is very diverse and complex, maybe we could use the term “rich”. Our work is very interesting, although difficult. The main rewarding outcome is the perception that the effort we devote to this project is an important contribution to the establishment of EOSC.

Julia

And, on the other hand, what has been challenging?

Luciano

The diversity of the actors and user communities as well as the existing silos, which are the result of different needs and aspirations of the different user communities, make implementing the EOSC quite challenging, but we are working on that.

Julia

Yes, I can imagine that it’s never easy to meet everyone’s needs – but I’m sure you all do your best! And what are your plans for the near future?

Luciano

After the end of EOSC- Pillar, I will continue contributing to the EOSC-Future activities concerning the onboarding of resources into the EOSC Catalogue. Additionally, from this September on I will also be involved in Skills4EOSC, one of the first Horizon Europe projects, which aims at advancing Open Science skills and coordinating support activities also through national competence centers, which are to be established at the national level. We will make them interoperable and connected at the European level.

Julia

So it never gets boring inside the EOSC! Thank you already for all your interesting insights, I have one last questions: If you could tell people one thing about EOSC, what would that be?

Luciano

Well, as I was saying in the beginning, EOSC was a very vague concept because it has a very broad scope and objective. For each implementation, it is very important that everyone contributes: With ideas, with technical contribution... EOSC cannot be really effective without the contribution of every single researcher. So my message is: Please join!

Julia

That's a very good message, I couldn't agree more! Dear listeners, let's make the EOSC your cloud!
So, Luciano, I thank you very much for your time and I wish you all the best for the future projects!

Luciano

Thank you very much, it was a pleasure to try to explain what EOSC is now and what it can be with your contribution!

Marie

Yes, thank you very much. I'm really looking forward to our next podcast episode, and I hope you listeners will join us for that!